

Open Music Europe Recorded Music Datasets

Antal, Dániel Vieira, Fabio Mester, Anna Márta
Poort, Joost Mikš, Tomáš
Tuukkanen, Roosa Helmi Henriikka

The datasets described in this document were created in the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action *Open Music Europe (OpenMusE) – An Open, Scalable, Data-to-Policy Pipeline for European Music Ecosystems* (Open Music Europe 2023).

Open Music Europe – ISRC-Sampled Sound Recording Metadata

The *Open Music Europe – ISRC-Sampled Sound Recording Metadata* dataset was created during testing various statistical sampling methodologies to describe better the distribution, diversity, circulation and income of music distributed on music streaming platforms. It is based on algorithmic samples sent against the Spotify API. We worked with Spotify because has provided traditional to most openness towards music metadata.

This dataset is a large, semantically lighter dataset that provides descriptive information about sound recordings. It is serialised into a CSV file with clearly defined variable mappings and into a simple RDF file in which each variable is linked to the corresponding ontology terms. This dataset supports large-scale statistical analysis and interoperability with other Open Music Observatory resources through its linked definitions.

The first version of the dataset contains 343,900 observations across 18 variables and is provided in CSV format. As an initial release, it contains missing values and reflects the current state of ongoing metadata harmonization and repair. Subsequent versions are expected to reduce missingness and expand coverage by incorporating additional observations and refinements.

The `openmuse_isrc_sampling_dataset_v1.csv` contains the data, and this document contains a human- and machine readable description of the dataset.

SKCMDb Dataset

The SKCMDb dataset is available in a database format at <https://hudobnadatabaza.sk/en/>. It provides a semantically rich description of sound recordings and related cultural heritage

entities associated with Slovak musical heritage and with recordings that fulfil the criteria for classification as national content under Slovak local content regulations.

This dataset is available in three complementary formats:

- a native Wikibase graph
- an RDF export serialised in Turtle format
- a faceted, user-oriented representation in the Sampo semantic browser

Each sound recording is represented as a dataset row and as a graph node. The graph includes detailed links to agents, the abstract musical works realised by each recording, and multiple access points for listening, downloading, or purchasing where permitted by rights and licensing conditions.

Livonian Dataset

The *Livonian Music Database* is a semantically rich dataset designed for aggregation into Europeana and integration into *Heritage Digital Twins* (for our ontological alignment, which may be the first try to apply this ontology to music is documented in (Antal 2025)) on the *European Collaborative Cultural Heritage Cloud*. It contains extensive cultural, linguistic, and contextual metadata needed for long-term preservation and interoperable dissemination of Livonian intangible cultural heritage.

It is accessible via <https://finnougric.net/en/>, choosing the “Music” perspective and selecting this database collection. We will separate publish its authoritative dataset linked to this document.

Karelian Dataset

The Karelian Music Dataset is a semantically rich dataset designed for aggregation into Europeana and for integration into *Heritage Digital Twins* on the European Cultural Heritage Cloud. It provides detailed metadata describing Karelian musical heritage and the cultural context in which the recordings were created, collected, or disseminated.

It is accessible via <https://finnougric.net/en/>, choosing the “Music” perspective and selecting this database collection. We will separate publish its authoritative dataset linked to this document.

Variables

The following variables are present in all datasets. The SKCMDb, Livonian, and Karelian datasets include their own human-readable and machine-readable data definitions, described in detail in the Annex of the Open Music Observatory documentation, which is available [here](#) (Antal 2024).

Sound recordings

A **sound recording** is the actual captured sound: a specific audio performance fixed in a sound file or master. Under the ISRC (International Standard Recording Code) standard, each distinct sound recording is identified by a unique ISRC. Different edits, remasters, or versions of the same performance typically receive different ISRCs, because they represent different sound recordings (ISO 2019).

Recording Title

variable name	recording_title
description	Title of the sound recording as provided in metadata
ontology alignment	title
notes	May be multilingual; language tags are applied when known

Normalised Recording Title (Identifier-style Alias)

variable name	normalised_recording_title
description	Deterministically normalised alias of the recording title
ontology alignment	
notes	Derived from <code>recording_title</code> by applying ASCII-only, uppercase normalization for identifier-style matching and reconciliation. This variable is an alias of the recording title, not a distinct work or title statement, and carries no ontological role. It is intended solely for technical matching, joining, and comparison, not for presentation or authoritative naming.

Artist Name (Spotify Display Artist)

variable name	artist_name
description	Presentation artist credited by Spotify
ontology alignment	creator
notes	Used only as a descriptive field; ontological roles must be assigned through curated agent statements

Normalised Artist Name (Identifier-style Alias)

variable name	normalised_artist_name
description	Deterministically normalised alias of the Spotify display artist name
ontology alignment	–
notes	Derived from <code>artist_name</code> by applying ASCII-only, uppercase normalization for identifier-style matching and reconciliation. This variable is an alias, not a separate artistic identity, and carries no ontological role. It is intended for technical matching, joining, and comparison only, not for presentation or authoritative naming.

Recording Lyrics Language

The recording lyrics language is only added to the Slovak, Livonian, and Karelian datasets.

variable name	recording_lyrics_language
description	Principal language of the lyrics in the recording
ontology alignment	language of work or name
notes	Empty or marked appropriately for instrumental recordings

Duration

variable name	duration
description	Duration of the sound recording
ontology alignment	duration
notes	Stored as milliseconds; semantically corresponds to ISO 8601 duration format

Identifiers

International Standard Recording Code

variable name	isrc
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description	International Standard Recording Code
ontology	ISRC , defined according to ISO 3901:2019 International Standard
alignment	Recording Code
notes	Primary, globally unique identifier of the sound recording

Country of ISRC Registration

variable	isrc_country_code
name	
description	Country code of the national ISRC issuing agency that allocated the registrant code
ontology	ISO 3166-1 alpha-2
alignment	location qualified with location applies to : country of ISRC registration
notes	This does not indicate the place of recording, artist nationality, or rights jurisdiction; and left NA (missing) if the code was not assigned by a national registration agency.

ISRC Registrant Code

For details on ISRC registration please see *International Standard Recording Code (ISRC) Handbook. 4th Edition.* (International ISRC Registration Authority 2021)

variable	isrc_registrant_code
name	
description	Registrant code assigned by the national ISRC agency identifying the organisation registering the recording
ontology	identifier (string) qualified with identifier type : ISRC registrant code
alignment	
notes	Distinguishes the label or distributor authorised to assign ISRCs

Year of ISRC Registration

variable	isrc_reference_year
name	
description	Two-digit year field from ISRC indicating the year in which the registrant assigned the code

ontology	has time qualified with temporal role : date of ISRC registration, precision:
align- ment	year
notes	This is the ISRC assignment year, not the recording year or release year

ISRC Country Code

The ISRC country code does not refer to a country as a geopolitical entity, but to an organisation that registers sound recordings with a territorial jurisdiction. For example, *Association of Hungarian Record Companies* (Mahasz, [omo:Q2035](#)), the Hungarian national IPI Group member, handles the ISRC codes starting with HU. In this respect, the HU part of the ISRC code does not refer to Hungary but to Mahasz.

In most cases, HU and other ISRC country codes coincide with the country code of the jurisdiction, but several large countries ran out of their identifier range, and have multiple top-level codes, like the U.S., Brazil or Germany; and ISRC reserved some top-level registration codes for technical purposes, too.

variable	isrc_country_code
name	
description	Two-character ISRC prefix identifying the allocating authority
ontology	identifier (string) omo:P37 , qualified with identifier type omo:P39 as ISRC
align- ment	registrant code omo:Q2037 .
notes	Extracted from the first two characters of the ISRC. Identifies the allocating authority according to ISO 3901 and IFPI practices. This does not necessarily correspond to the country of the artist, label, or release.

ISRC Registration Country

For example, *Association of Hungarian Record Companies* (Mahasz, [omo:Q2035](#)), handles the registrations on the territory of Hungary. Whenever the top-level registrar corresponds with a geopolitical entity, we placed the entity's name in this variable, including non-sovereign entities like Hong Kong or French Southern Territories. The non-territorial codes are marked with *No agency [exception]*.

Our aim was the study of Slovak and Hungarian registrations in and outside of their registrars, and the algorithms we used collected a lot of identifiers that fell out of the scope of these countries.

variable	isrc_registration_country
name	
description	Resolved allocating authority associated with the ISRC prefix

ontology	—
align- ment	
notes	Indicates the national ISRC agency's location, or a non-standard or unassigned category. This field reflects allocation practice, not distributor, label, or rights ownership.

ISRC Designation Code

This range usually identifies a label or a rights management company that handles recording-side royalties. The reason why they cannot be directly mapped to labels is that certain designation codes were allocated to labels that were dissolved, or merged into newer entities, or have other successors. They can be seen as a provenance variable for the particular registration. Unfortunately, we know that often the same recording receives new ISRC codes when the previous registering body or its administration records are no longer available.

variable	isrc_designation_code
name	
description	Registrant-internal sequential identifier that distinguishes recordings assigned in the same year
ontology	identifier (string) qualified with identifier type : ISRC designation code
align- ment	
notes	Unique within a registrant and year; not a globally unique identifier

Spotify Track ID

variable name	spotify_track_id
description	Platform-specific identifier for the recording on Spotify
ontology	Spotify track ID
alignment	
notes	Used as an access point; not a persistent identifier and not legally or semantically authoritative

Release

A **release** is a packaged publication of one or more recordings made available to the public. In DDEX terminology, a release groups recordings together in a specific commercial or distribution context, such as an album, single, EP, or digital compilation. The same recording can appear on multiple releases (for example, an album release, a single release, and a compilation), while retaining the same ISRC.

Unfortunately, as our research shows, new releases often receive a new ISRC code.

Release Year

variable	release__year
name	
description	Year in which the release became publicly available
ontology	has time qualified with temporal role : date of release, precision: year
align- ment	
notes	Derived from release date for analysis and grouping

Release Name

variable name	release__title
description	Title of the release containing the recording
ontology	title of the release entity
alignment	
notes	Refers to the release, not the recording

Normalised Release Name (Identifier-style Alias)

variable name	normalised__release__title
name	
description	Deterministically normalised alias of the release name
ontology	
align- ment	
notes	Derived from the release name by applying ASCII-only, uppercase normalization for identifier-style matching and reconciliation. This variable is an alias of the release name, not a distinct release entity or title statement, and carries no ontological role. It is intended exclusively for technical matching, joining, and comparison, not for presentation or authoritative naming.

Release Type

variable name	release__type
description	Classification of release as album, single, or compilation
ontology	Maps to subclasses of release in the Annex (single , album , compilation)
alignment	

notes	Follows the release categories used in Spotify metadata
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UPC or EAN

The *Open Music Europe – ISRC-Sampled Sound Recording Metadata* does not contain release identifiers, and not in all cases in the smaller datasets.

variable name	upc
description	Universal Product Code or European Article Number identifying the release
ontology alignment	UPC or EAN
notes	Identifies the release entity, not the recording

Label Name

We provide this information when it is given. It is not provided in the *Open Music Europe – ISRC-Sampled Sound Recording Metadata*, and not in all cases in the smaller datasets.

variable name	label_name
description	Label or imprint text supplied via Spotify metadata
ontology alignment	record label
notes	This is a descriptive imprint only; rights-bearing organisations must be identified separately

Label Identifier (Curated)

This information is not given in the case of the *Open Music Europe – ISRC-Sampled Sound Recording Metadata*, and not in all cases in the smaller datasets.

variable name	label_identifier
description	Unique identifier for the label or rights-holding organisation
ontology alignment	identifier (URL) or identifier (string) , with identifier type

notes Often an ISNI, ROR, OpenCorporates, or internal OMO identifier

Copyright Notice © (Sound Recording)

We use this information, where given, to try to infer the label, but we will not include this variable in the dataset. This is not provided in the Open Music Europe – ISRC-Sampled Sound Recording Metadata.

variable name	copyright_P
description	Phonogram copyright holder for the sound recording
ontology alignment	rights
notes	Indicates rights in the sound recording itself

References

- Antal, Daniel. 2024. “Open Music Observatory.” Digital Music Observatory. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16539570>.
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